

Repeated *in vitro* exposure to PFOA impairs intestinal barrier integrity and leads to cytosolic accumulation as detected by subcellular chemical imaging

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Intestinal co-culture with mucus cells reduces basolateral [¹⁴C]-PFOA passage.
- Acute PFOA exposure increases ATP production by intestinal cells at high concentrations.
- Repeated PFOA exposure progressively impairs intestinal barrier integrity even at low concentrations.
- Subcellular chemical imaging enables PFOA localisation in cytosol of cells.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) is a persistent organic pollutant recognised for its environmental presence and bioaccumulation, despite regulatory restrictions under the Stockholm Convention. While systemic effects of PFOA have been studied extensively, its interaction with the first biological barrier encountered after oral exposure, the gastrointestinal barrier, remains poorly characterised. In this study, we evaluated the fate, uptake and effects of PFOA in human intestinal cell culture models after acute (24 h) and repeated (11-day) exposures. Using radiolabelled PFOA profiling, we found that PFOA was not metabolised by Caco-2 cells nor by HT29-MTX mucus-producing cells, in monocultures or in co-culture. Mass balance studies revealed higher basolateral passage of PFOA in Caco-2 monocultures compared to Caco-2/HT29-MTX co-cultures, suggesting that the mucus in the co-culture may trap PFOA and limit its passage. These observations led us to conduct further toxicological evaluations in the Caco-2 monoculture model. Acute exposure, while having no effect on cell viability, increased cellular ATP at highest exposure concentration. Repeated exposure led to a progressive concentration-dependent decrease in trans-epithelial electrical resistance, indicating a compromised barrier function. This effect was not

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linked to changes in tight junction gene expression, but rather attributed to cell death. High-resolution chemical imaging revealed intracellular accumulation of PFOA in Caco-2 cell cytosol after repeated exposure. These findings highlight the potential of repeated exposure to PFOA, even at low concentrations, to impair intestinal barrier integrity, which may have implications for systemic absorption and toxicity.

1. Introduction

Since the early 1950s, a wide variety of industrial products, including those used in food manufacturing, waterproof textiles, carpeting and firefighting foam, have been manufactured using perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA). This compound belongs to the chemical class of perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), a subset of the large anthropogenic group of perfluorinated compounds. It is composed of a hydrophilic end group and a hydrophobic, lipophobic alkyl chain in which all carbon-hydrogen bonds (C–H) are replaced by fluorine bonds (C–F). As a result of its covalent fluorocarbon bonds, the PFOA molecule is resistant to high temperatures as well as chemical and biological degradative reactions, allowing it to be extremely persistent in the environment (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2017) and bioaccumulate in humans and animals, with an estimated half-life of 3 to 8 years, depending on levels and duration of exposure (Bartell et al., 2010; Seals et al., 2011).

Human and animal exposure to PFOA primarily occurs through contaminated drinking water and food. Food contamination, as for other PFAS, is primarily attributed to two mechanisms: bioaccumulation in aquatic and terrestrial food chains (Bedi et al., 2023; Bao et al., 2019), and migration from food contact materials used during processing and packaging, such as non-stick cookware coatings (Trier et al., 2011). Numerous studies have detected PFOA not only near manufacturing facilities and areas with a history of intensive firefighting activities (Filipovic et al., 2015; Wee and Aris, 2023), but also in remote regions like the Arctic (AMAP, 2017). Its presence in polar environments highlights its potential for long-range transport and environmental persistence (Cai et al., 2012; Kwok et al., 2013). PFOA is one of the most commonly detected PFAS in Arctic ecosystems, including wild foods traditionally consumed by Inuit populations (e.g., fish, beluga, whales, polar bear, seal) (AMAP, 2017, 2021; Fraley et al., 2023; Kelly et al., 2009; Murcia-Morales et al., 2025).

In the 1960s, first toxicological studies concerning the human health risks of PFOA exposure were published. Employees of a 3 M manufacturing plant exposed to perfluorinated compounds displayed high levels of PFOA in their serum (Olsen et al., 1998), which were subsequently linked to health outcomes such as birth defects and ulcerative colitis (Fart et al., 2021; Steenland et al., 2013; Stein et al., 2014). Research combining epidemiological evidence in humans and toxicological studies in animal models has since shown that PFOA exposure is associated with a broad spectrum of adverse health effects, including immunotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, disruption of endocrine hormones (promoting hypothyroidism), kidney dysfunction and an elevated risk of several cancers (including testicular, prostate, kidney, and ovarian) (Coperchini et al., 2017; Leonard et al., 2008; Liang et al., 2022; Vieira et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2014).

Yet, relatively few studies have examined the impact of PFOA on intestinal health, at the forefront of oral exposure, and the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) toxicity of PFOA remains largely unknown. In particular, there is very limited data available on PFOA in *in vitro* intestinal cell models.

Based on this background, the present work aims to evaluate the GIT toxicity of PFOA *in vitro* under acute and repeated exposure scenarios, focusing on uptake, fate and toxicity studies. For the fate and uptake analysis, [¹⁴C]-PFOA was used in three intestinal epithelial cell models: (i) a Caco-2 monoculture, widely used to simulate the intestinal barrier; (ii) a monoculture of HT29-MTX mucus-secreting cells; and (iii) a Caco-2/HT29-MTX co-culture, which mimics a more physiologically relevant

mucus-producing epithelium. Toxicity assessment was performed exclusively on the Caco-2 monoculture and included cell viability assays, real-time trans-epithelial electrical resistance (TEER) measurements and analysis of associated markers of intestinal barrier integrity (i.e., tight junction (TJ) genes). To gain further insight into the uptake and fate of PFOA, its intracellular localisation was also investigated using high-resolution chemical imaging, specifically in the context of repeated exposure in the Caco-2 monoculture. For this purpose we used the latest generation of mass spectrometer consisting of a Focused Ion Beam (FIB) coupled with Secondary Ion Mass spectrometry (SIMS) technique (De Castro et al., 2022), a technique previously validated for localising PFOA in Caco-2 cells following acute exposure (Stoffels et al., 2024), now employed for the first time to explore its localisation under repeated exposure.

2. Material and methods

A schematic representation of the overall experimental design is presented in Fig. 1.

2.1. Intestinal cell lines and cell culture conditions

Human colon adenocarcinoma Caco-2 cell line was obtained from the European Collection of Cell Cultures (ECACC, UK). Mucus-secreting colon adenocarcinoma HT29-MTX cell line was kindly provided by Dr. Thécla Lesuffleur (INSERM, France). Cells were used at passages 49–55 for Caco-2 and 9–15 for HT29-MTX. Both cell lines were maintained in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM, Sigma, France) containing 4.5 g/L glucose. The medium was supplemented with 1 % (v/v) penicillin/streptomycin (Sigma, France), 1 % (v/v) non-essential amino acids (NEAA; Gibco, France), 1 % (v/v) Glutamax (Gibco, France), and 10 % (v/v) heat-inactivated foetal bovine serum (FBS, Sigma, France). Cells were cultured at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere of 5 % CO₂/95 % air. This culture medium was changed every two to three days (300 µL in apical compartment and 900 µL in basolateral compartment) and cells were split upon confluence with Tryple Express (Gibco, France). For all experiments, cells were seeded at a density of 150,000 cells per cm² either in 96-well plates (Corning Costar, Germany) or on 6.5 mm polycarbonate membrane inserts with a 1 µm pore size (Millipore, France). In co-culture conditions, a 90:10 ratio of Caco-2 to HT29-MTX cells was used.

2.2. PFOA stock solution preparation

Perfluorooctanoic acid ammonium salt (PFOA) (Sigma-Aldrich, Belgium) was weighed and dissolved in Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO) (Sigma-Aldrich, Belgium) to prepare a 40 mM PFOA stock solution. Aliquots (50 µL) of the stock solution were stored at –20 °C.

2.3. Cell exposure to PFOA

Starting day 10 after seeding, FBS from the culture medium was substituted with 1 % (v/v) Insulin Transferrin Selenium (ITS) to limit any interference with PFOA. For treatment, PFOA stock solution (40 mM) was diluted 10 or 100 times in DMSO to prepare intermediate solutions of 4 mM and 0.4 mM, corresponding to final treatment concentrations of 10 µM and 1 µM, respectively. The 40 mM, 4 mM, and 0.4 mM PFOA solutions were then added to the culture medium at 0.25 % (v/v) DMSO to achieve final concentrations of 100 µM, 10 µM, and 1 µM,

Gold™ liquid scintillation cocktail (PerkinElmer, France) were added to each sample. Samples were counted in a liquid scintillation analyser (Tri-Carb 2910TR, PerkinElmer). Sample quenching was compensated by the use of quench curves and external standardisation. To determine mass balance results, each experiment was performed in three biological replicates.

2.4.1.1. Radioprofiling. Apical and basolateral media samples were analysed by HPLC on an Ultimate-3000 Liquid Chromatography apparatus (ThermoFisher Scientific, France) connected for radioactivity detection to a Flo-One 625TR instrument (PerkinElmer SAS, France) using 2 mL/min FloScint II as the scintillation cocktail (PerkinElmer), with a 500 µL detection cell. PFOA and metabolites (if any) were monitored by on-line radioactivity detection and were quantified by integrating the area under the detected peaks.

The HPLC system consisted of a Zorbax SB C₁₈ column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm) (Agilent Technologies, USA). Mobile phases consisted of A: ammonium acetate buffer (20 mM, pH 3.5 adjusted with acetic acid)/acetonitrile (95:5; v/v) and B: acetonitrile (100 %). The temperature was maintained at 25 °C, the flow rate was 1 mL/min and the following gradient was used: 0–4 min 100 % A; 4–6 min 100 % A to A:B 70:30 v/v; 6–21 min A:B 70:30; 21–23 min A:B 70:30 to 50:50; 23–33 min A:B 50:50; 33–34 min A:B 50:50 to 100 % B; 34–44 min 100 % B; 44–45 min 100 % B to 100 % A; 45–60 min 100 % A.

2.4.2. Cell metabolic activity (ATP assay, CellTiter-Glo®)

To evaluate the viability of differentiated Caco-2 cells grown on 96-well plates and treated with PFOA for 24 h (at concentrations of 1, 10 and 100 µM), cell metabolic activity was evaluated by quantifying adenosine triphosphate (ATP) in the cells. Following the 24-h exposure, the plates were equilibrated at room temperature for 30 min. The culture medium containing PFOA was removed, and 50 µL/well of fresh culture medium were added. While protecting the assay from light exposure, 50 µL/well of CellTiter-Glo® Reagent (Promega, France) were added, and the plates were mixed for 2 min on an orbital shaker to induce cell lysis. After a 10-min incubation at room temperature, luminescence was recorded using a microplate reader (Spark 20 M, Tecan, Belgium). The reported values are expressed as a percentage of the negative control (*i.e.*, unexposed cells).

2.4.3. Cell proliferation (CyQuant® assay)

The CyQUANT cell proliferation assay (ThermoFischer Scientific, France) was used to assess cell density in culture. Prior to staining, the plates were equilibrated to room temperature. Then, 200 µL/well of the dye 80-fold diluted in the 1 × cell-lysis buffer were added to the plates. The plates were then incubated for 5 min at room temperature in the dark. Fluorescence was measured at an excitation wavelength of 480 nm and an emission wavelength of 520 nm (Spark 20 M, Tecan, Belgium).

2.4.4. Cell proliferation (In-Cell Western assay)

2.4.4.1. Fixation and staining. After 24-h exposure, cells were fixed using 4 % paraformaldehyde (Electron Microscopy Sciences, USA) for 20 min at room temperature, followed by permeabilisation using 0.1 % Triton. A fluorescently labelled CellTag™ 700 stain (accumulating in both the nucleus and cytoplasm of permeabilised cells; LICORBio, France) diluted 1/2000 times was applied to determine the cell number. Between each step, the wells were washed 3 times using MAXWash buffer (Active Motif, Belgium). At last, 200 µL of MAXBlock medium (Active Motif) were added to each well before image acquisition.

2.4.4.2. Image acquisition and quantification. Plates were scanned using a Sapphire™ Biomolecular Imager (Azure Biosystems, USA); fluorescence plate reader, with excitation/emission wavelengths set to 675/697 nm). Fluorescence intensity corresponding to CellTag™ 700 stain

was quantified using AzureSpot. Raw absorbance data were averaged for the duplicates and corrected for background. The relative (to control) fluorescence units obtained from the scanning were used to perform a quantitative analysis.

2.5. Repeated exposure assays

2.5.1. Trans-epithelial electrical resistance

The trans-epithelial electrical resistance (TEER) of Caco-2 monocultures was continuously monitored using a cellZScope version 2 system (nanoAnalytics, Germany). Cells were grown on polycarbonate membrane inserts in 10 % (v/v) FBS medium until day 9 and transferred to the cellZScope device for a 24-h stabilisation in the same medium. At day 10, basal TEER values were measured. The medium was then removed and cells were repeatedly exposed at the apical side to PFOA (concentration of 1, 10 and 100 µM) vs control for 11 days as previously described. Medium was replaced every two to three days with DMEM plus 1 % (v/v) ITS. TEER was monitored every day during the 11-day exposure period. Three independent experiments were performed.

2.5.2. Gene expression

After exposure, total RNAs were extracted from cells for each insert using the AllPrep RNA Mini kit (Qiagen, France) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Quantity and quality of extracted RNA samples were monitored using Nanodrop (Nanophotometer Implen, Dutscher, France) and Bioanalyser (Agilent Technologies, USA), respectively. RNAs (250 ng/sample) were reverse transcribed using enzyme IScript reverse transcription supermix (Biorad, France). 384-well plates were completed by an Agilent Bravo Automated Liquid Handling Platform (Agilent Technologies, France). All wells contained 5 µL of the following mix: 2.5 µL of IQ SYBR green Supermix (Biorad, France), 1.5 µL of primers and 1 µL of cDNA sample (diluted x10 after RT). Amplification was performed using a QuantStudio 5 (Applied Biosystem, USA). Thermal cycling conditions were as follows: 3 min denaturation at 95 °C followed by 40 cycles at 95 °C for 15 s and 45 s at 60 °C, and a melting curve step. Primer sequences of the targeted genes *i.e.*, genes encoding TJ proteins (zonula occludens-1, *ZO-1*; occludin, *OCN*; representative members of the claudin family, *CLDN1*, *CLDN3*, *CLDN4*, *CLDN7*) are listed in Table S1. Raw data that passed quality control were analysed with LinRegPCR (version 2021.2) and then normalised to housekeeping 5.8S ribosomal RNA expression.

2.5.3. Cytotoxicity assay (LDH assay, CytoTox-96® non-radioactive assay)

To evaluate the cytotoxic effect of PFOA on Caco-2 cells in 96-well plates at 21 days of differentiation, after 11 days of repeated cell exposure to 1, 10 and 100 µM PFOA, cell membrane integrity was assessed by measuring the release of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH). LDH is a cytosolic enzyme, which is released into the cell culture medium in case the plasma membrane is damaged. At day 21, 50 µL/well of the exposure medium were transferred in another plate and incubated with 50 µL LDH-substrate (Promega, France). After 10 min, 50 µL of the stop solution were added. For the positive control (maximum LDH release), cells were previously lysed using Triton X-100. The fluorescence was measured at an excitation wavelength of 530 nm and an emission wavelength of 590 nm (Spark 20M, Tecan, Belgium). The reported values are expressed as a percentage of negative control (*i.e.*, unexposed cells).

2.5.4. Cell proliferation (In-Cell Western assays)

To assess cell proliferation over time of cells repeatedly exposed to PFOA (at concentrations of 1, 10 and 100 µM) starting on day 10, an In-Cell Western assay was performed at days 13, 15, 17, and 21 of culture as described above in Section 2.4.4.

2.5.5. High-resolution chemical imaging of PFOA

2.5.5.1. Sample preparation. At the end of the exposure period (day 21) to PFOA (concentration of 1, 10 or 100 μM), inserts were fixed in 2 % glutaraldehyde in 0.1 M Sorensen phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) overnight at 4 °C, washed overnight in 0.2 M phosphate buffer and then post-fixed for 1 h at room temperature with 1 % osmium tetroxide in 250 mM saccharose and 0.05 M phosphate buffer. The samples were then dehydrated in a series of graded ethanol solutions (0 %, 30 %, 50 %, 70 % and 90 %; VWR, Belgium) for 10 min each, and afterwards 2 h for the 100 % solution; membranes were cut out from the wells and embedded in an Epon resin (Embed 812, Electron Microscopy Sciences). Finally, samples were cut into 300-nm semi-thin sections using an ultramicrotome (Leica, Austria), placed on polished silicon wafers (Siltronix, France), and coated with a 5-nm gold film using sputtering instrument (Leica, Austria).

2.5.5.2. FIB-SIMS. The SIMS analysis was performed with a FIB instrument (Scios, Thermo Fischer, The Netherlands), coupled with a compact mass spectrometer developed at the Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST; De Castro et al., 2022) using a Ga⁺ primary source with an energy of 30 keV. The surface of the sample was rasterised with a pattern of 30 × 30 μm^2 with a primary current of 50 pA, which should give an estimated spatial resolution of around 100 nm. The masses studied simultaneously in multicollection mode were the negative ions ¹⁹F⁻ (m = 15.995 amu), ¹²C¹⁴N⁻ (m = 26.003 amu) and ³⁵Cl (m = 34.969 amu, not presented here). The images were recorded in a pixel format of 512 × 512 image points with a counting time of 2 ms per

pixel (~8 min per acquisition).

2.6. Statistical analysis

Statistical significance was calculated using one-way or two-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparison test, after testing for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test (when normality was not confirmed, Kruskal-Wallis test was applied) with the GraphPad Prism software version 10.4.1 for Windows (GraphPad Software, USA). Power analysis was conducted using G*Power software version 3.1.9.7 for Windows (Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf, Germany) to ensure adequate sample sizes for detecting biologically relevant differences with at least 95 % power. Biological replicates (n), are indicated in the figure legends; the number of technical replicates (tech. reps) per biological replicate is also reported where applicable. Data are expressed as the mean + standard deviation (SD) for bar graphs, and standard error of the mean (SEM) for XY graphs, and minimum to maximum values for box plots. Differences were considered statistically significant for a p-value less than 0.05.

3. Results

3.1. Acute exposure to PFOA: distribution and metabolism of PFOA in Caco-2, HT29-MTX and Caco-2/HT29-MTX cell cultures and effects on Caco-2 cell viability

[¹⁴C]-radiolabelled PFOA was used to assess PFOA distribution (mass balance analysis) and metabolism in different cell culture

Fig. 2. Effects of 24-h acute exposure on PFOA distribution across intestinal cell models. Caco-2, HT29-MTX, and Caco-2/HT29-MTX cell cultures were exposed to [¹⁴C]-radiolabelled PFOA at a concentration of 1, 10, or 100 μM for 24 h. PFOA distribution was assessed across three compartments: apical side, basolateral side and cellular fraction including the membrane insert. (a) Distribution profile in Caco-2 monoculture (b) Distribution profile in HT29-MTX monoculture (c) Distribution profile in Caco-2/HT29-MTX co-culture. Quantification of radioactivity enabled evaluation of PFOA passage and accumulation patterns across the different cell models. Values represent recovered radioactivity, and error bars indicate standard deviation (SD) of replicates ($n = 3$; tech. rep. = 3), reported with the precision of the first significant figure.

compartments (i.e., apical compartment, cellular fraction including the membrane insert, and basolateral compartment). Total radioactivity recovery was within satisfactory ranges between $97.4 \pm 12\%$ and $103 \pm 11\%$ for the Caco-2 cell monoculture, between $87.9 \pm 0.95\%$ and $99.3 \pm 6.7\%$ for the HT29-MTX cell monoculture, and between $90.3 \pm 2.8\%$ and $96.9 \pm 11\%$ for the co-culture, depending on the exposure concentrations (Fig. 2). Regarding PFOA distribution across the different compartments, no concentration-dependent effect was observed in HT29-MTX monoculture and in the co-culture; however, in Caco-2 cell monoculture, at concentrations lower than $100\ \mu\text{M}$, a higher level of radioactivity was recovered in the basolateral compartment, and a lower level in the apical compartment, compared to the $100\ \mu\text{M}$ concentration (Fig. S1). For each exposure concentration, radioactivity in the basolateral compartment was significantly higher for the Caco-2 cell monoculture ($64 \pm 8\%$; $61 \pm 11\%$; $53 \pm 1\%$, for $1\ \mu\text{M}$, $10\ \mu\text{M}$ and $100\ \mu\text{M}$ respectively) than for the co-culture ($38 \pm 3\%$; $36 \pm 2\%$; $37 \pm 4\%$, for $1\ \mu\text{M}$, $10\ \mu\text{M}$ and $100\ \mu\text{M}$ respectively) (Fig. S2). Whatever the cell model, no [^{14}C]-PFOA metabolite was detected on radio-HPLC profiles in apical and basolateral compartments (Fig. S3), indicating that intestinal cells do not metabolise PFOA under the tested conditions, which aligns with the European Food Safety Authority report (Schrenk et al., 2020). Hence, potential toxic effects would be directly linked to PFOA exposure. The Caco-2 monoculture exhibited the highest level of PFOA passage to the basolateral compartment, likely due to the absence of a mucus layer that, in the co-culture, may retain PFOA and limit its passage. As this increased passage may be associated with increased susceptibility to toxic effects, we focused our subsequent assays on Caco-2 monocultures. Cell metabolic activity assessment, using an ATP assay, shows that 24-h acute exposure to PFOA had no effect on ATP-production at $1\ \mu\text{M}$ and $10\ \mu\text{M}$, but surprisingly a significantly greater amount of ATP was detected ($p < 0.0001$) in cell lysates at the highest concentration of $100\ \mu\text{M}$ (Fig. 3a). To investigate whether this difference was linked to the number of cells producing ATP (i.e., to cell viability) or to the cellular metabolism itself, we performed cell counting using In-Cell Western and CyQuant. Both assays indicated that PFOA exposure did not affect cell number compared to controls (Fig. 3b, c).

3.2. Repeated exposure to PFOA: consequences on gut barrier integrity in Caco-2 monocultures

Measurement of TEER is classically used to assess the integrity and permeability of cell monolayers (Brun et al., 2014; García-Rodríguez et al., 2018; Vila et al., 2018). TEER was here monitored *in situ* and in real time with the cellZScope system for Caco-2 cells grown on polycarbonate membrane inserts and repeatedly exposed to PFOA at

concentrations of 1 , 10 and $100\ \mu\text{M}$ for 11 days starting day 10 of cell differentiation. TEER decreased in a PFOA concentration-dependent manner and then stabilised over time (Fig. 4a). Starting 24 h after exposure at the concentration of $100\ \mu\text{M}$, the TEER value was significantly reduced compared to the control ($p < 0.0001$). On the second day of exposure, the TEER reduction became significantly different from the control for the $10\ \mu\text{M}$ concentration as well ($p = 0.0005$). The $1\ \mu\text{M}$ exposure had a significant impact on TEER after 10 days of exposure.

Given that TEER primarily depends on the presence and function of TJ proteins, we assessed the expression of several genes encoding TJ proteins (*OCLN*, *TJP1*, *CLDN2*, *CLDN3*, *CLDN4*, *CLDN7*) to support this concentration-dependent TEER profile. However, no changes in the expression of selected genes, *TJP1* and *OCLN* (Fig. 4b, c), as well as *CLDN2*, *CLDN3*, *CLDN4*, *CLDN7* as members of the claudin family (Fig. S4), were observed in response to repeated exposure to PFOA at 1 , 10 or $100\ \mu\text{M}$.

Since TEER reflects the integrity of the cell monolayer, with damaged or incomplete cell layers typically displaying lower TEER, we measured cell cytotoxicity following repeated exposure to PFOA. Interestingly, cytotoxicity, assessed by measuring the release of LDH, increased at PFOA $1\ \mu\text{M}$ and $10\ \mu\text{M}$ ($p = 0.0158$ and $p = 0.0079$, respectively), but not at $100\ \mu\text{M}$ (Fig. 4d). The amount of LDH released being influenced by cell number, we investigated cell count using In-Cell Western assays. After just 3 days of PFOA exposure at $100\ \mu\text{M}$, a significant decrease ($p < 0.0001$) in cell number was observed (Fig. 4e). Starting at 5 days of exposure, an increasing variability in cell number was observed for the wells exposed to $10\ \mu\text{M}$ ($\text{SD}_{3\text{-day exposure}} = 20.36\%$ vs $\text{SD}_{5\text{-day exposure}} = 52.35\%$) (Fig. 4f, g). At the end of the exposure period, the decrease in cell number was significant at the $10\ \mu\text{M}$ concentration ($p < 0.0001$), and a certain variability was starting to settle in for the lowest concentration of $1\ \mu\text{M}$ ($\text{SD}_{10\text{-day exposure}} = 38.96\%$) (Fig. 4h). Given the decrease in cell number (i.e., cell death) measured starting at 3 days of exposure at $100\ \mu\text{M}$ (Fig. 4e), the absence of increased LDH release at the highest dose (Fig. 4d) is probably due to early cell death and subsequent LDH degradation, rather than reduced cytotoxicity.

3.3. PFOA localisation in Caco-2 cells after repeated exposure

To gain more insight into the uptake and fate of PFOA, which was initially demonstrated using mass balance analysis for acute exposure (Fig. 2), high-resolution chemical imaging using FIB-SIMS was performed to unravel PFOA intracellular localisation at the subcellular level on the Caco-2 monoculture following 11-day repeated exposure at concentrations of 1 , 10 and $100\ \mu\text{M}$. The elemental distribution of $^{19}\text{F}^-$ and $^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}^-$ in cells is shown in Fig. 5, where PFOA localisation was

Fig. 3. Effects of 24-h acute PFOA exposure on cell viability in Caco-2 monocultures. Caco-2 cells were exposed to PFOA at a concentration of 1 , 10 or $100\ \mu\text{M}$ for 24 h. Cell metabolic activity was measured using the ATP-based CellTiter-Glo assay (a), while cell number was assessed using the In Cell-Western assay (b) and the CyQuant assay (c). All results are expressed as a percentage of the control (i.e., untreated cells). Data are presented as min-to-max box plots of replicates ($n = 3$; tech. rep. = 15). Significant differences are indicated with asterisks (**** $P < 0.0001$ vs controls).

a) **TEER**

b) **TJP1**

c) **OCN**

d) **Cytotoxicity (LDH released)**

e) **Cell number after 3-day exposure**

f) **Cell number after 5-day exposure**

g) **Cell number after 7-day exposure**

h) **Cell number after 11-day exposure**

(caption on next page)

Fig. 4. Effects of 11-day repeated PFOA exposure on TEER, TJ gene expression, and cytotoxicity in Caco-2 monocultures. Caco-2 cells were repeatedly exposed to PFOA at a concentration of 1, 10, or 100 μM every two days, from day 10 to day 21 of differentiation. (a) TEER was measured *in situ* and in real time using the cellZScope system on cells cultured on membrane inserts. Error bars represent standard error of the mean (SEM) of replicates ($n = 3$; tech. rep. = 5). (b, c) Relative mRNA expression levels of TJ markers *TJP1* (ZO-1) and *OCN* were assessed after 11-day repeated exposure by qPCR on cells grown on polycarbonate membrane inserts. Data are presented as min-to-max box plots of replicates ($n = 3$; tech. rep. = 5) (d) Cytotoxicity was evaluated after 11-day repeated exposure using the LDH assay on cells cultured in 96-well plates, and is expressed as a percentage of the control (*i.e.*, untreated cells) Data are presented as min-to-max box plots of replicates ($n = 2$; tech. rep. = 15). (e–h) Cell number was estimated by In Cell-Western assay on cells grown in 24-well plates 3, 5, 7 and 11 days after exposure. Fluorescence is expressed as a percentage of the control and shown as min-to-max box plots. Fluorescence images are shown beneath the corresponding quantification panels, with each row representing one of four representative replicates per condition. Data are presented as min-to-max box plots of replicates ($n = 2$; tech. rep. = 7) Significant differences are indicated with asterisks (* $P < 0.05$, **** $P < 0.0001$ vs controls).

achieved by monitoring fluoride ions ($^{19}\text{F}^-$, red), while the cellular structure was identified using carbon-nitrogen molecular ions ($^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}^-$, green). FIB-SIMS imaging enabled localisation of PFOA after exposure at 10 and 100 μM at the subcellular level, with a preferential localisation in the cell cytoplasm. PFOA appears to be diffusely distributed throughout the intracellular space but largely excluded from apparent nuclear regions. It is important to note that these FIB-SIMS images provide qualitative elemental maps illustrating PFOA presence and distribution, serving as visual support for the quantitative PFOA uptake data presented in Fig. 2. However, at the 1 μM PFOA exposure concentration, no distinct fluoride signal could be reliably detected by FIB-SIMS. This is likely due to the technical sensitivity limitations of the instrument at this low cellular concentration, where the localised amount of fluorine may fall below the detection threshold, despite PFOA being present in the cellular fraction, as observed in bulk measurements (Fig. 2).

4. Discussion

Industrialised populations are typically exposed to PFOA through contaminated food, drinking water and household products (Li et al., 2022; Schrenk et al., 2020). According to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the mean dietary exposure to PFOA in European adults is estimated to range from 0.13 to 0.28 ng/kg body weight (bw) per day in the lower bound and from 3.60 to 5.71 ng/kg bw per day in the upper bound, making PFOA the second predominant contributor to dietary exposure to PFAS, following PFOS (Schrenk et al., 2020). Some populations experience far higher levels of exposure, particularly individuals working in PFAS manufacturing plants or residing in areas with heavily contaminated drinking water (Li et al., 2020; Pitter et al., 2020; Wee and Aris, 2023). For example, individuals who consumed well water near a fire training area in Germany had PFOA blood plasma levels ranging from 4.0 to 18 ng/mL (Weiss et al., 2012). Similarly, in northern Italy, people who raised and consumed their own livestock and vegetables using well water near a former industrial plant that produced PFASs for decades had serum PFOA levels as high as 750 ng/mL (Ingelido et al., 2020). The most alarming blood concentrations are seen in a Chinese study (Fu et al., 2016; Gao et al., 2015), reporting up to 32,000 ng/mL of serum PFOA in workers at a fluorochemical manufacturing plant, which is about 16,900 times higher than the median serum PFOA concentration (1.9 ng/mL) in European adults reported by EFSA (Schrenk et al., 2020). However, we should not ignore that more remote populations face a unique exposure profile due to their reliance on traditional dietary habits. Arctic communities, for example, are particularly vulnerable due to their consumption of traditional, wild-harvested foods. In fact, marine animals such as beluga whale and seals, central to Inuit diets, are known to bioaccumulate considerable levels of contaminants, including PFOA (AMAP, 2017, 2021), making their dietary intake a significant contributor to internal exposure (Aker et al., 2024; Long et al., 2015; Murcia-Morales et al., 2025). Biomonitoring studies have recorded serum concentrations in Arctic residents (1.36 ng/mL in East Greenland; 2.2 ng/mL in Nunavik, Canada; 1.23 ng/mL on Faroe Islands; 4.8 ng/mL in Iceland) that rival or exceed those seen in some industrialised populations (Adlard et al., 2024; Sonne et al., 2023).

These findings demonstrate the existence of a wide range of exposure scenarios involving different doses. The concentrations tested in this

work (1 μM , 10 μM and 100 μM corresponding to 414 ng/mL, 4140 ng/mL and 41,400 ng/mL respectively) are substantially higher than the average serum concentration in European adults (1.9 ng/mL \approx 0.0046 μM) or in remote populations exposed through contaminated traditional diets. However, they are within the range of exposure reported for highly exposed populations, particularly those residing near industrial source (Gao et al., 2015; Ingelido et al., 2020; Weiss et al., 2012).

As PFOA is mostly associated with dietary intake, the first barrier to exposure is the gastrointestinal tract (GIT). In order to evaluate the GIT toxicological impact of PFOA, three *in vitro* cell models were considered, the first one was a culture of enterocytes alone (Caco-2 monoculture), the second one, mucus-secreting cells alone (HT29-MTX), and the third one consisted of a co-culture of Caco-2/HT29-MTX cells, seeded at 90 % and 10 %, respectively. This specific 90:10 ratio has been widely adopted in the literature as it provides a physiologically relevant *in vitro* model of the intestinal epithelium, combining both robust barrier properties and effective mucus secretion (García-Rodríguez et al., 2018; Gillois et al., 2021; Pan et al., 2015). All these cell models were first exposed to PFOA at different concentrations for 24 h. Striking differences in PFOA distribution were observed between Caco-2, HT29-MTX and Caco-2/HT29-MTX cell cultures, highlighting the influence of cell model. In particular, the basolateral presence of PFOA was significantly lower in co-culture conditions than in monoculture Caco-2 conditions. Consistent with previous observations on other food contaminants (Gillois et al., 2018) and due to its physical and chemical properties, mucus might trap PFOA, reducing its passage through the intestinal barrier, by limiting its access to Caco-2 cells. Interestingly, we observed a reduced basolateral passage of PFOA in Caco-2 monocultures at 100 μM , suggesting that passage into the basolateral compartment may become saturated above a certain concentration threshold. Kimura and colleagues previously investigated uptake in Caco-2 cells with regard to transporter-mediated mechanisms and showed that apical uptake of PFOA was partially inhibited by OATP blockers, indicating that organic anion transporting polypeptides (OATPs) contribute to PFOA uptake (Kimura et al., 2017, 2020). However, the mechanisms underlying the full transport dynamics of PFOA across the intestinal epithelium remain to be elucidated.

Further GIT toxicity assessment was performed on Caco-2 cell monoculture. Following 24-h exposure, cell viability remained unchanged across all concentrations tested. However, a significant increase in intracellular ATP levels was observed at 100 μM PFOA, which was not accompanied by an increase in cell number. This suggests that cells may respond to high concentrations of PFOA after 24 h of exposure by adapting to meet elevated energy demands, potentially in preparation for further stress conditions (Marchetti et al., 2020). Alternatively, previous studies have shown that stress-inducing treatments can increase mitochondrial number and ATP. For example, Zinc Oxide nanoparticle-treated Caco-2 cells contained more mitochondria, which, however, appeared enlarged and perforated (Mittag et al., 2021). Moreover, doxorubicin-treated senescent cells displayed mitochondrial hyper-function, characterised by increased mitochondrial mass, elevated mitochondrial DNA, and higher ATP levels. Importantly, these hyper-functional mitochondria were found to act as both the source and the target of elevated ROS, forming a vicious cycle that ultimately led to mitochondrial damage, depolarisation of the membrane potential, and

Fig. 5. PFOA localisation inside Caco-2 cells after 11-day repeated exposure. Elemental distribution of $^{19}\text{F}^-$ (first column) and $^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}^-$ (second column) in 300-nm-thick section of (a) control cell and (b, c, d) exposed cells to PFOA. The last column shows the corresponding overlap of $^{19}\text{F}^-$ (red) and $^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}^-$ (green). Cells were exposed to (b) 1 μM PFOA, (c) 10 μM PFOA and (d) 100 μM PFOA. The fluoride signal allows the localisation of PFOA at the subcellular level in the biological structures identified by the $^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}^-$ signal. Scale bar is 5 μm .

apoptosis at later stages of senescence (Wang et al., 2016). Additional studies assessing mitochondrial count and function (e.g., membrane potential or respiratory capacity) would be helpful in determining an adaptive response and/or mitochondrial dysfunction following PFOA exposure. Stoffels and colleagues assessed PFOA toxicity and impact on metabolic activity in Caco-2 cells after acute 24-h exposure, and, similarly to our results, no notable impact on cell viability was detected (Stoffels et al., 2024). While a mild increase in metabolic activity was noted at concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 100 μM , this was not accompanied by increased ATP production, except at the highest dose tested (500 μM), which aligns with the increase we observed at 100 μM . While our findings and those of Stoffels and colleagues (Stoffels et al., 2024) indicate no significant impact of PFOA on Caco-2 cell viability following 24-h exposure, in a very recent study, Zou and colleagues reported a 24-h acute exposure of Caco-2 cells to PFOA at concentrations between 12 μM and 241 μM was sufficient to reduce cell viability (Zou et al., 2025). This effect was linked to increased intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) and mitochondrial dysfunction, and suggests a cellular stress response at concentrations where we did not detect cytotoxic effects. Several factors may contribute to the apparent discrepancies between our results and those of Zou and colleagues. Although both studies used Caco-2 cells, the cell lines originated from different sources (Procell Biotechnology Co., Ltd., China in (Zou et al., 2025) versus ECACC, UK (this study)), and passage numbers were not reported in their study. Culture medium composition also differed, such as the presence of FBS in (Zou et al., 2025) versus its absence in our medium from day 10 of differentiation, which could influence PFOA bioaccessibility and/or bioavailability. Finally, differences in viability assessment may play a role: in (Zou et al., 2025), cell viability was measured using the CCK-8 assay following 24-h exposure, while we assessed PFOA cytotoxic effects, combining ATP assay, cell number by In-Cell Western and CyQUANT assay (Fig. 3). Previously, PFOA was shown to affect the viability of human colon carcinoma (HCT116) cells in a time- and dose-dependent manner (Kleszczyński et al., 2007), and more recently, Solan and colleagues found that Caco-2 cells are relatively less sensitive to PFOA, compared to other tested human cell types (e.g., hepatoma cell line, HepaRG; microglial cell model, HMC-3; and skeletal muscle cell line, RMS-13) (Solan et al., 2022).

Our study addressed, for the first time, the influence of a repeated PFOA exposure regimen (every two days from day 10 of differentiation for 11 days) at different concentrations, with a special emphasis on intestinal barrier integrity. This approach provides a more physiologically relevant perspective compared to single-concentration or acute exposure scenarios. Real-time and *in situ* cellZScope measurements of Caco-2 cells repeatedly exposed to PFOA revealed a concentration-dependent decrease in TEER before time stabilisation, as an indicator of possible intestinal barrier impairment. For the highest exposure concentration (100 μM), we observed a significant decrease in TEER after only 24 h. Similarly, Zou and colleagues observed a significant decrease in TEER and increased permeability, accompanied by a reduction in occludin protein expression, after 24-h exposure at 241 μM . While both findings suggest that PFOA can impair gut barrier function at high concentrations within 24 h, their study was limited to a single, high-concentration acute exposure. In contrast, our work extended this understanding by investigating repeated low-to-moderate exposures over time, offering a more comprehensive and environmentally relevant assessment of barrier integrity. Notably, even the lowest tested concentration (1 μM) resulted in a statistically significant TEER reduction after 10 days, highlighting the susceptibility of the intestinal barrier to prolonged low-concentration PFOA exposure. The fact that we observed TEER reductions and cytotoxicity at low doses only after prolonged exposure further underscores the value of chronic models in revealing subtle, cumulative effects that may be overlooked in acute settings. In order to understand the decrease in TEER, which was not associated with changes in TJ gene expression in our study, in contrast to the TJ effects reported by Zou and colleagues at more than twice the maximal

concentration tested in our study (i.e., 240 μM versus 100 μM) (Zou et al., 2025), we analysed cell cytotoxicity using an LDH quantification assay. After 11 days of exposure, we observed a significant increase in LDH release for the 1 μM and 10 μM concentrations, indicating a higher rate of cell death in these conditions. This suggests a cytotoxic effect of PFOA towards Caco-2 cells after repeated exposure. Surprisingly, this effect was not observed at 100 μM . Given the 9-h half-life of extracellular LDH, this absence likely reflects earlier cell death and subsequent LDH degradation, rather than reduced cytotoxicity at the highest concentration. This finding was consistent with the cell counting using In-Cell Western analysis; as early as day 2 of exposure, cell number at the highest concentration was significantly reduced compared to the control. At 10 μM , a decline in cell number began around day 4 (i.e., intra-group variability increased), with statistical significance reached only after 11 days of exposure. For the lowest concentration (1 μM), after 11 days of exposure, increased intra-group variability indicated the onset of cytotoxic effects, although the overall decrease in cell number was less pronounced. We examined the gene expression of key regulators of cell cycle arrest and apoptosis (p21 and p53), but no significant changes were detected (data not shown). The underlying mechanism of cell death remains therefore to be elucidated.

To gain further insight into PFOA uptake by Caco-2 cells after 11-day repeated exposure, we used a FIB-SIMS platform, a high-resolution imaging technique that enabled its spatial mapping at subcellular level. A conventional FIB platform consists of scanning the sample with a finely focused ion beam of sub-nm resolution for machining (e.g., FIB lamella preparation). At the same time, the ionic bombardment generates emission of secondary electrons that can be used to provide morphology and structure of the surface raster. In addition, the FIB platform used for this study was equipped with a high-performance magnetic sector Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometer (SIMS) system, developed by the LIST (De Castro et al., 2022). The integrated FIB-SIMS instrument allows for the acquisition of both high-resolution structural information and elemental/chemical information from the same field of view. In this study, we focused on the detection and localisation of two ions: fluorine $^{19}\text{F}^-$ and the $^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}^-$ ion. Due to its high electronegativity, fluorine is readily detectable by SIMS, enabling a high detection sensitivity, this enables the spatial mapping of fluorine within cells and thus the tracking of PFOA (Eybe et al., 2008). The $^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}^-$ ion is a cluster commonly used in SIMS to visualise the biological substructure in cells and tissues, linked to variations in protein concentration, giving contrasted images very similar to those obtained by optical microscopy. Using this elemental/chemical information, we detected PFOA in the cells exposed to concentrations higher than or equal to 10 μM . Below 10 μM , specifically at the 1 μM exposure concentration, no distinct fluorine signal could be reliably detected. This observation, however, is likely due to the technical sensitivity limitations of the FIB-SIMS instrument for fluorine at such low local cellular concentrations, where the absolute amount of PFOA within the analysed voxel may fall below the practical detection threshold. This does not necessarily imply that, at 1 μM , PFOA was not retained by the cells after repeated exposure, as supported by our own liquid scintillation counting data for acute exposure (Fig. 2) showing the presence of PFOA even at this concentration in the cell fraction (including the membrane insert), and also by the study by Stoffels and colleagues showing PFOA uptake by Caco-2 cells at concentrations as low as 0.1 μM . When detected, PFOA was localised in the cytosol of Caco-2 cells, similarly to the observations of Stoffels and colleagues (Stoffels et al., 2024). This interpretation is based on the observed diffuse intracellular distribution of the $^{19}\text{F}^-$ signal, largely confined within the cell boundaries (as indicated by the $^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}^-$ signal) and its apparent exclusion from distinct organellar structures or the nucleus. While Stoffels and colleagues were the first to demonstrate PFOA localisation in Caco-2 cells following acute exposure using this approach, our study extends this application to repeated exposure conditions, offering new perspectives on its cellular dynamics (Stoffels et al., 2024). Given its physicochemical properties, with a hydrophobic and

lipophobic perfluorinated carbon chain, and a charged functional group (*i.e.*, carboxylic acid) that gives one end of the molecule slight hydrophilicity, it is not surprising that PFOA localises in the cytosol. Additionally, PFOA is known to have a protein-philic character, which stems from the peculiar interaction between a perfluorinated methyl group, *i.e.*, the last carbon of its chain, and a carbonyl group in proteins' backbone (Tiburtini et al., 2024). This likely promotes its association with cytosolic proteins, which might disrupt their function.

While this study provides valuable insights into the distribution and toxicity of PFOA across different intestinal cell models, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, inherent constraints associated with *in vitro* models must be considered. Although Caco-2 and HT29-MTX are widely used to simulate the intestinal barrier, including mucus as a key protagonist, they are immortalised cancer-derived cell lines and do not fully reflect the physiological complexity of primary human intestinal cells (*e.g.*, differentiation, and enzyme and transporter expression). Compared to *in vivo* models, these models lack cellular diversity (*e.g.*, enteroendocrine or immune cells), stromal interactions, gut microbiota, and fail to reproduce the dynamic mechanical and biochemical environment of the gastrointestinal tract, all of which play key roles in regulating intestinal permeability and xenobiotic metabolism. In this study, while PFOA distribution was analysed across Caco-2 and HT29-MTX monocultures and Caco-2/HT29-MTX co-culture models, toxicity assessment was limited to the Caco-2 monoculture. Future studies should assess toxicity under more complex conditions, including organoid-based systems. Moreover, it should be noted that TJ protein abundance and localisation were not assessed in this study, however, our gene expression data support the fact that the observed TEER decrease after repeated PFOA exposure is primarily associated with cell death rather than TJ changes. Additionally, although our findings suggest that mucus may reduce PFOA uptake due to its trapping properties, we did not explore the possibility of using FIB-SIMS to detect and localise PFOA within the mucus layer, due to anticipated limitations in sample preparation, particularly with regard to the dehydration steps that would compromise the mucus integrity. Finally, while this study included, for the first time, repeated exposure conditions, future work should investigate the effects of lower environmentally relevant PFOA concentrations to better model typical population exposure and potential chronic effects.

In conclusion, the results of this study demonstrate that after a 24-h acute exposure, [¹⁴C]-PFOA distribution within compartments was different depending on the cell model with a preferential passage for Caco-2 cells, probably due to the trapping properties of mucus secreted by HT29-MTX cells (and/or inside the mucus-containing vesicles). While ATP production increased, cell viability remained unchanged at 100 μM PFOA exposure, for Caco-2 cells. During repeated PFOA exposure, a TEER decrease was observed in a concentration-dependent manner, which was not related to an altered TJ gene expression, but rather to a decrease in cell number. Importantly, this study provides the first *in vitro* investigation of repeated PFOA exposure across a range of concentrations, an approach that better reflects real-world scenarios and allows simulation of various exposure levels relevant to different population groups, including workers or Indigenous communities potentially facing chronic environmental contamination. As a novelty in the field, high-resolution chemical imaging allowed us to detect and localise PFOA in the cell cytosol and provided insights into its intracellular fate and uptake in support of toxicity assessment. Further work will continue in this direction to simulate the complexity of real-world environmental exposures, where PFOA may co-occur with other pollutants, such as particulate plastics, which may influence its fate, uptake and biological effects.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Melanie Mobley: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Mathilde Leveque: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Charlotte B.A. Stoffels:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Elodie Person:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Sandrine Bruel:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Isabelle Fourquaux:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Hervé Robert:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Nicolas J. Cabaton:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jean-Nicolas Audinot:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Muriel Mercier-Bonin:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Chat GPT in order to improve the formulation of some sentences. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication. No AI tools were employed in the analysis or interpretation of the data.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.180666>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

All illustrations have been created in BioRender: Eutamene, H. (2025) <https://BioRender.com/5dbrw6r>; Eutamene, H. (2025) <https://BioRender.com/ut1d6ne>.

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Glossary

FIB-SIMS stands for Focused Ion Beam - Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry. It is a high-resolution analytical technique that combines:

- Focused Ion Beam (FIB): A finely focused beam of ions (typically Ga⁺ ions) is used to precisely raster (scan) the sample surface, causing the ejection (sputtering) of surface atoms and molecules.
- Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (SIMS): This detects and analyses the secondary ions (charged particles) ejected during sputtering. These ions are directed into a mass spectrometer, where their mass-to-charge ratios are measured, providing detailed chemical composition of the sample surface.